

Formulation of a Mass-Based Population Balance Equation: Insights Into Derivation, Mass Transfer, and Nondimensionalization

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Abstract

Population balance equations (PBEs) are well-suited for modeling properties of dispersed phases such as bubbles, droplets and solid particles in processes. Unlike commonly used momentum and energy balance equations, PBEs transcend external spatial coordinates, incorporating internal property dimensions such as length, shape, and concentration. This study focuses on transforming the traditional number-based PBEs into a mass-based formulation, offering superior characteristics and insights in engineering applications. The mass-based formulation results in a conservative equation which allows the evaluation of breakage and coalescence kernels as well as the numerical method for mass conservation. The transformation introduces a new source term describing mass increase from outside the balanced system, confirming an approach origin from kinetic gas theory published by other authors. The study addresses challenges in discretizing the coalescence birth term denominator by nondimensionalization of the PBE. This research enhances our understanding of PBE modeling, particularly with the inclusion of mass transfer, contributing valuable insights for engineering applications.

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1. Introduction

Population balance equations (PBEs) are very useful for describing the properties of bubbles, droplets, solid particles, etc. in the following just particles and their complex behavior in multi-phase disperse flows [1–7]. The unique feature of PBE modeling is that it does not rely solely on the external physical space coordinates (e.g., x, y, z) commonly used in mass, momentum, and energy balance equations. Instead, PBE incorporates the consideration of transport processes within property space using internal coordinates such as length, shape, and concentration. This allows highly complex processes such as particle breakage, coalescence, growth and nucleation and their effect on the variables like interfacial area density and their distribution over these properties to be studied on a statistical basis with a single transport equation.

Traditionally, PBEs are formulated in a non-conservative number-based framework, which quantifies the population in terms of discrete entities like bubbles [1, 5], droplets [3] or solid particles [6]. However, in many practical engineering applications, it is more convenient and insightful to work with conserved quantities such as mass, species mass, energy and momentum. In order to couple the PBE with these quantities and to be able to map phenomena such as reaction, mass and heat transfer, a conservative mass-based formulation is more appropriate. This work explores the transformation of a number-based PBE into a mass-based one and highlights its significance in engineering contexts.

The mass-based formulation was already introduced and applied to bubble columns by Jakobsen and coworkers [8–11]. In their earlier work Sporleder *et al.* [8], a simple transformation was carried out without taking mass transfer into account. In a subsequent work of Nayak *et al.* [9], new transport equations and variables (mass and momentum) were derived on the basis of the kinetic gas theory (KGT) for the dispersed gas phase, which, like the PBE, also have internal coordinates. Vik *et al.* [10] then finally extended the theory to non-isothermal systems with mass transfer within their kinetic theory approach with size resolution (KTAWSR), introducing a particle size, time and spatial position dependent mass, species mass, momentum and energy balance of the dispersed phase.

In their PBE resp. the size-dependent mass balance of the dispersed gas phase, a new term for mass transfer was found, which describes the mass transfer in addition to the one in the growth term. In this work, we also derive the additional mass transfer term independently of Vik’s approach and discuss the relevance and necessity of the term. The authors are aware that parts of this work have already been considered in other publications. However, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, a common and detailed derivation and discussion of the mass-based PBE is missing in the literature.

Starting from a number-based PBE the mass-based formulation transforms the PBE into a conservative transport equation. This transformation has the advantage of validating the breakage

and coalescence kernels and the numerical solution method for mass conservation. In addition, the value of the distribution density function is drastically scaled, which allows an easier and more accurate numerical solution of the PBE [12]. After the transformation, an additional mass transfer source appears in the mass-based formulation, which describes the mass increase due to mass transfer from outside the considered dispersed phase. Our approach from the field of continuum mechanics confirms the correctness of this additional term resulting from the KTAWSR. We found the deeper origin of this term, and the conservation property of the growth rate is discussed and explained.

However, the transformation to a mass-based formulation generates, among other things, a new denominator in the coalescence birth term, which is numerically difficult to discretize. As a possible solution, we propose a way to nondimensionalize the PBE. Overall, this work contributes to a better understanding of PBE modeling, especially when mass transfer between phases is included.

2. The Number-Based Population Balance Equation

Utilizing a local instantaneous continuum mechanical framework about the modeled system resp. the considered dispersed phase, we can formulate a multidimensional transport equation governing the conserved density function, denoted as ψ , within the phase space \mathbf{C} . This formulation is achieved through the application of the generalized theorems of Gauss and Stokes, as elucidated in Supplementary Information S.1.1. The phase space \mathbf{C} is conventionally partitioned into physical space, characterized by external coordinates $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)^\top$, and property space, defined by internal coordinates $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots)^\top$. A comprehensive derivation is available in Jakobsen [13] and Ramkrishna [14] and a summary is provided in Supplementary Information S.1.

$$\frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot (\psi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) \mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t)) + \nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \cdot (\psi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) \mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{c}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t)) = \Phi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) \quad (2.1)$$

In the context of Eq. (2.1), t represents the time dimension, $\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}$ and $\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{c}}$ denote velocities in physical and property space, respectively, and Φ represents a source or sink within the phase space.

It should be noted here that, strictly speaking, Eq. (2.1) is only an equation for single-phase systems. In the context of the continuum mechanical framework, for an application to multiphase systems, integral theorems which are generalized to include discontinuities (phase boundary) and averaging procedures, e.g. volume averaging, would have to be applied. This procedure causes additional terms describing the exchange between the phases and turbulence. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this has not yet been done. However, the single-phase PBE has been used successfully in multiphase systems for decades [1–7].

Given the presence of a time derivative and a first-order partial differential operator in Eq.(2.1), it necessitates appropriate initial and boundary conditions. Typically, an open domain is considered in physical space, implying the existence of both inlet and outlet fluxes, with one being specified by the boundary condition. In the properties space, a partially open system is commonly examined, where a flux occurs at a single boundary, such as the nucleation flux at the lower limit. A detailed discussion is available in Ramkrishna [14], with a concise summary presented in Supplementary Information S.1.3.

The number-based PBE emerges by assigning the conserved density function ψ to number density function $f_{\text{d}}^{\text{n}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t)$.

$$\frac{\partial f_{\text{d}}^{\text{n}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) f_{\text{d}}^{\text{n}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t)) + \nabla_{\mathbf{c}} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{c}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) f_{\text{d}}^{\text{n}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t)) = \Phi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) \quad (2.2)$$

In most engineering applications, only one inner coordinate in the property space is included, usually the particle size ξ [3–6], which simplifies the PBE to Eq. (2.3), which is called number-based PBE (nPBE) in the following.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f_d^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) \\ = -B_D^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + B_B^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - C_D^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + C_B^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

Here, $v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$ is the velocity in property space with respect to the 1D particle size dimension in the following just growth rate. In addition, an n has been super-scripted to indicate that this growth rate originates from the number-based formulation. The source term Φ is decomposed into components representing breakage ($B_B^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$, $B_D^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$) and coalescence ($C_B^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$, $C_D^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$) phenomena, encompassing birth and death events. These terms are formulated through macroscopic considerations, with derivations provided in works by Jakobsen [13] and Solsvik *et al.* [15] or Ramkrishna [14]. Their expressions are articulated as follows:

$$B_D^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = b(\xi) f_d^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \quad (2.4)$$

$$B_B^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{\xi}^{\xi_{\max}} \nu P(\xi, \zeta) b(\zeta) f_d^n(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t) d\zeta \quad (2.5)$$

$$C_D^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = f_d^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{(\xi_{\max}^3 - \xi^3)^{1/3}} c(\xi, \zeta) f_d^n(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t) d\zeta \quad (2.6)$$

$$C_B^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\xi^2}{2} \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{(\xi^3 - \xi_{\min}^3)^{1/3}} \frac{c([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \zeta)}{(\xi^3 - \zeta^3)^{2/3}} f_d^n(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^n([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \mathbf{r}, t) d\zeta \quad (2.7)$$

where $b(\xi)$ is the breakage frequency, ν is the average number of daughter particles after breakage, $P(\xi, \zeta)$ is the daughter size distribution function, ξ_{\max} , ξ_{\min} are the maximum and minimum particle sizes, ζ is the integration variable or the mother particle, and $c(\xi, \zeta)$ is the coalescence frequency. The upper integration limits for coalescence terms have been modified by Jakobsen [13] to ensure strict mass conservation, as explained in detail in Solsvik *et al.* [15]. Additionally, Solsvik *et al.* [11] introduces Heaviside functions before birth and death terms to further enforce mass conservation – a practice endorsed by the authors but is not replicated in this work for brevity.

3. Transformation from Number-Based to Mass-Based PBE

The number-based density function, f_d^n , typically assumes values on the order of $1 \times 10^8 \text{ m}^{-4}$, especially in gas-liquid systems. The precision of numerical calculations becomes a challenge for such large numbers, as they are prone to round-off errors [12]. To address this, the number-based density distribution function, f_d^n , can be transformed and scaled by the single particle mass $m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$, where ξ is typically in the micrometer range. This transformation results in a mass-based density distribution function, f_d^m . The scaling operation significantly diminishes the magnitude of f_d^n , allowing for more accurate numerical calculations while maintaining the integrity of the underlying physical system. The relationship for transforming f_d^n to f_d^m is expressed as:

$$f_d^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \quad (3.1)$$

To effect the transformation, Eq. (3.1) is incorporated into Eq. (2.3). Subsequently, each term in Eq. (2.3) is individually converted, expanded, and then combined.

Accumulation term

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \right) = \frac{1}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} - \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)^2} \frac{\partial m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} \quad (3.2)$$

Convection in the physical space

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \left(\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \right) &= \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \\ &+ \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \\ &- \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)^2} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Convection in the property space

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \left(v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \right) &= \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{\partial v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial \xi} \\ &+ \frac{v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial \xi} \\ &- \frac{v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)^2} \frac{\partial m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial \xi} \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

Source and sink terms

$$B_D^{m,*}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = b(\xi) \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \quad (3.5)$$

$$B_B^{m,*}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{\xi}^{\xi_{\max}} \nu P(\xi, \zeta) b(\zeta) \frac{f_d^m(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)} d\zeta \quad (3.6)$$

$$C_D^{m,*}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{(\xi_{\max}^3 - \xi^3)^{1/3}} c(\xi, \zeta) \frac{f_d^m(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)} d\zeta \quad (3.7)$$

$$C_B^{m,*}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\xi^2}{2} \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{(\xi^3 - \xi_{\min}^3)^{1/3}} \frac{c([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \zeta) f_d^m(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)}{(\xi^3 - \zeta^3)^{2/3} m_d(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)} d\zeta \quad (3.8)$$

$$\frac{f_d^m([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \mathbf{r}, t)} d\zeta$$

If the Eq. (3.2) - Eq. (3.8) are multiplied by $m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$ and combined, the following equation results:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} - \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{\partial m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + \mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \\ & - \frac{\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \frac{\partial v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial \xi} + v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial \xi} \\ & - \frac{v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{\partial m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial \xi} = -B_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + B_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - C_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + C_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

By applying the chain rule in reverse, the two convection terms can be condensed once more. Additionally, the term $\frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}$ is bracketed out before the partial derivatives of the particle mass; this yields the following result.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) \\ & - \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \left(\frac{\partial m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \frac{\partial m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial \xi} + \mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \right) \quad (3.10) \\ & = -B_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + B_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - C_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + C_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \end{aligned}$$

The use of the total time derivative, that is $\frac{d\phi(t, x_1(t), \dots, x_N(t))}{dt} = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{dx_i}{dt} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_i}$, enables the summarization of the partial derivatives related to the mass of a single particle, resulting in the final equation Eq. (3.11) that is subsequently referred in the following text as number to mass-based PBE (n2mPBE).

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (v_{\xi}^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) \\ & = \frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) dt} - B_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + B_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - C_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + C_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

In which now:

$$B_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = b(\xi) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \quad (3.12)$$

$$B_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \int_{\xi}^{\xi_{\max}} \nu P(\xi, \zeta) b(\zeta) \frac{f_d^m(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)} d\zeta \quad (3.13)$$

$$C_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{(\xi_{\max}^3 - \xi^3)^{1/3}} c(\xi, \zeta) \frac{f_d^m(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)} d\zeta \quad (3.14)$$

$$C_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{\xi^2 m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{2} \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{(\xi^3 - \xi_{\min}^3)^{1/3}} \frac{c([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \zeta)}{(\xi^3 - \zeta^3)^{2/3}} \frac{f_d^m(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\zeta, \mathbf{r}, t)} d\zeta + \frac{f_d^m([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d([\xi^3 - \zeta^3]^{1/3}, \mathbf{r}, t)} d\zeta \quad (3.15)$$

In order to be in line with the equations presented in [5, 9–11, 16], only the definition of the mass density of the dispersed phase ρ_d , that is $m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}) = \rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) V_d(\xi)$, where $V_d(\xi)$ is the volume of a single particle with size ξ , has to be applied. The term $dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)/dt$ must be described with a appropriate closure.

4. Discussion

4.1. Extra Mass Transfer Term

The comparison of the nPBE (Eq. (2.3)) and the n2mPBE (Eq. (3.11)) shows that the transformation from a number-based PBE to a mass-based PBE leads to an additional term that appears on the right side of the n2mPBE (Eq. (3.11)), the extra mass transfer term that is $\frac{f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt}$. This term represents an additional mass transfer term beside the one within the convection term in the property space (growth). It accounts for the increase in total mass of the dispersed phase that is balanced in the PBE caused by a mass flux from outside, e.g. the continuous phase, into the dispersed phase.

In order to get a deeper understanding of the origin of the extra mass transfer term, we start with substituting ψ in the generalized PBE Eq. (2.1) with the mass density function f_d^m and assume only one inner coordinate, the particle size, so that the mass-based PBE (Eq. (4.1)), in the following just mPBE, directly follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (v_{\xi}^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) f_d^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)) \\ = -B_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + B_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - C_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) + C_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

Comparing the mPBE (Eq. (4.1)) with the one from the transformation of the number-based PBE the n2mPBE (Eq. (3.11)), the extra mass transfer term is also missing here. The fact that the extra mass transfer term appears in the mass-based PBE through the derivation of the number-based PBE with subsequent transformation and does not appear in the direct derivation via the generalized PBE Eq. (2.1), can be attributed to the conservation properties of the original equation. To study the conservation property of the original equations the generalized PBE Eq. (2.1) is integrated over the entire phase space and Gauss's theorem is applied.

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = \int_{\Omega_{\mathbf{C}}(t)} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} d\mathbf{C} = \int_{\Omega_{\mathbf{C}}(t)} \Phi d\mathbf{C} - \oint_{\delta\Omega_{\mathbf{r}}(t)} \psi \mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}} \cdot d\mathbf{r} - \oint_{\delta\Omega_{\mathbf{c}}(t)} \psi \mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{c}} \cdot d\mathbf{c} \quad (4.2)$$

This equation implies that the conserved quantity Ψ changes temporally by a source within the modeled system (first term) and due to convective (second and third term) across the boundary of the modeled system. Note the conserved quantity Ψ is also the total quantity of the modeled system.

Now, from the observation in Section 2 that the PBE is a single-phase equation, it follows that if mass is considered as a conserved quantity, the integral over the source must disappear, since there are no internal sources of mass in a single-phase system, neglecting relativistic phenomena.

Consequently, the conserved quantity cannot change by convection within the domain, only by fluxes across the boundaries. This conclusion leads to two insights:

1. In a closed domain (no particles are added or withdrawn through fluxes across the boundary of the phase space) where no breakage and coalescence occurs, the following holds:
 - both the nPBE (Eq. (2.3)) and the n2mPBE (Eq. (3.11)) conserve the total number and not necessarily the total mass
 - the mPBE (Eq. (4.1)) conserves the total mass but not necessarily the total number

The fact that the nPBE (Eq. (2.3)) and the n2mPBE (Eq. (3.11)) have the same conservation properties is because Eq. (3.1) is a bijective mapping.
2. The velocities $\mathbf{v}_r, \mathbf{v}_c$ should be Ψ conservative, transporting it without generating or destroying it.¹ Hence, the growth rate v_ξ^n in the nPBE (Eq. (2.3)) is total number conserving, and in the mPBE (Eq. (4.1)), the growth rate v_ξ^m is total mass conserving.

Particle growth in one-dimensional length property space, without assumptions (refer to Supplementary Information S.2), correlates with changes in volume, which arise from changes in density and mass of the particle. Density changes maintain total mass and number. Mass changes can either preserve total number, involving mass transfer from outside modeled system e.g. from the continuous phase in to the dispersed phase due to phase changes or it can preserve total mass, involving mass transfer from within the modeled system, such as between neighboring particles sizes. Furthermore, it can preserve both total number and mass within the system, for instance, via mass transfer between non-neighboring particles sizes. Physically, only the number-conserving mass change due to phase change is pertinent, as the other mechanisms lack a phase boundary necessary for mass transfer or involve changes in the number of particles, typically modeled through breakage or coalescence. Therefore the number conserving growth rate v_ξ^n should contain both effects density change and mass change due to phase change and the mass conserving growth rate v_ξ^m only the density change:

$$v_\xi^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{\xi}{3\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{d\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} + \frac{1}{\frac{\pi}{2}\xi^2\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} \quad (4.3)$$

$$v_\xi^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{\xi}{3\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{d\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} \quad (4.4)$$

In summary, when considering mass transfer between phases leading to changes in the total mass of the dispersed phase, the use of either the nPBE (Eq. (2.3)) or the n2mPBE (Eq. (3.11)), is necessary, rather than relying on the mPBE (Eq. (4.1)). The n2mPBE (Eq. (3.11)) is superior to the nPBE (Eq. (2.3)) in most scenarios due to its aforementioned advantages, including scalability, interpretability, and the preservation of a conserved quantity.

If the previous findings and interpretations from the continuum mechanical model are compared with those from the kinetic gas theory model of Vik *et al.* [10], they are consistent. For instance,

¹At this point, this conclusion only applies mathematically strictly to mass as a conserved quantity, since the sources do not disappear after integration in the number-based PBE. However, if it is included that the behavior of the collective can be derived from the individual particle behavior and that the individual particle growth is number conserving, this statement applies again.

the model of Vik *et al.* [10] also features the extra mass transfer term. In terms of applicability, the KTAWSR already provides mass-based and size-dependent transport equations for the common conservation quantities (mass, species mass, momentum, energy). Whereas the approach from continuum mechanics presented in this work so far only applies to mass. A derivation based on a continuum mechanics approach, wherein the extra mass transfer is a direct outcome without detour over the number-based PBE, and in which new transport equations for the other conservation quantities, which also depend on the particle size, is currently absent in the literature. A potential avenue for this involves a derivation within the generalized phase space akin to that of multifluid equations (cf. Jakobsen [13]). However, this remains a subject for future work whereby the challenge must also be faced that the most of the experimental data or correlations available in the literature are for v_{ξ}^n and not for v_{ξ}^m .

4.2. Mass-based Breakage and Coalescence Sources and Sinks

As mentioned earlier, if mass is selected as the conserved quantity, the integral of ξ over Φ must vanish. Since breakage and coalescence are considered independent phenomena, this conclusion must also apply to both phenomena individually. Consequently, the mass of particles that undergo breakage or coalescence must be equivalent to the mass generated by breakage or coalescence. This ensures that, during the integration over the entire property space, the following relationship must hold:

$$0 = \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} B_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - B_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) d\xi \quad (4.5)$$

$$0 = \int_{\xi_{\min}}^{\xi_{\max}} C_B^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) - C_D^m(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) d\xi \quad (4.6)$$

Note that the mass-based terms Eq. (3.12) - Eq. (3.15) were obtained on the basis of a transformation of a number-based form. A direct derivation of the mass-based terms should be possible analogous to [13–15], but is not shown here.

The two relationships Eq. (4.5) and Eq. (4.6) of the mass-based breakage and coalescence kernels represents an additional advantage of the mass-based formulation over the number-based counterpart. For a number-based formulation with binary breakage or coalescence, the ratio of the integrals over the entire property space of the birth and death terms is 2 and 1/2 respectively. However, this only applies to binary processes. For breakage and coalescence phenomena in which different numbers of particles participate, e.g. size-dependent or location-dependent, this no longer applies, whereas in the mass-based formulation the relationship Eq. (4.5) and Eq.(4.6) is still valid.

Furthermore in the case of absent mass transfer the entire mass-based PBE is now in conservative form, ensuring that the system's conservation properties are rigorously preserved, enhancing numerical stability and accuracy. This characteristic facilitates the examination of kernel functions and employed numerical methods for mass conservation. It is important to note that this property extends to the general source Φ within the multidimensional property space.

Comparing the coalescence birth term in the mass-based formulation C_B^m with its number-based counterpart C_B^n , a noticeable difference, the single particle mass resp. the product of volume and density, arises in the denominator of the integral due to the transformation (see Eq. (3.15)). Since ξ and ζ generally fall in the millimeter or micrometer range, their difference results in an exceedingly small number, further compounded by applying the volume. Consequently, the entire denominator (see Eq. (3.15)) becomes very small, particularly at the respective integration limits, posing several numerical challenges. Firstly, division by an extremely small number yields a large number, making the system highly sensitive to small disturbances in f_d^m . Secondly, pronounced step gradients at integration limits pose challenges for accurate integration, crucial for maintaining mass conservation. Additionally, higher-order interpolation schemes, such as orthogonal collocation [5, 11], face difficulty in approximating step gradients without introducing oscillations. A potential resolution involves scaling the property space, prompting the subsequent nondimensionalization of the PBE.

4.3. Nondimensionalization of the PBE

To nondimensionalize the PBE, the dependent variable is identified as f_d^m , while the independent variables include $\xi, \mathbf{r}, t, \zeta$. Each variable is then expressed in terms of a dimensionless variable (indicated by a hat over the symbol) and a scaling factor (indicated by a subscript s) with units corresponding to the original variable. In the present case it follows:

$$f_d^m = \hat{f}_d^m f_{d,s}^m \quad (4.7)$$

$$t = \hat{t} t_s \quad (4.8)$$

$$\mathbf{r} = \hat{\mathbf{r}} r_s \quad (4.9)$$

$$\xi = \hat{\xi} \xi_s \quad (4.10)$$

$$\zeta = \hat{\zeta} \xi_s \quad (4.11)$$

If the Eq. (4.7)-Eq. (4.11) are inserted into Eq. (3.11), where we applied the definition of the mass density of the dispersed phase, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{f_{d,s}^m}{t_s} \frac{\partial \hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t})}{\partial \hat{t}} + \frac{f_{d,s}^m}{r_s} \nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} \cdot \left(\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\hat{\xi} \xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}} r_s, \hat{t} t_s) \hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) \right) + \frac{f_{d,s}^m}{\xi_s} \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\xi}} \left(v_{\xi}(\hat{\xi} \xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}} r_s, \hat{t} t_s) \hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) \right) \\ &= \frac{f_{d,s}^m}{\xi_s^3} \frac{\hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t})}{V(\hat{\xi})} \frac{1}{\rho_d} \frac{dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} - B_D^m(\hat{\xi} \xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}} r_s, \hat{t} t_s) + B_B^m(\hat{\xi} \xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}} r_s, \hat{t} t_s) \\ & - C_D^m(\hat{\xi} \xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}} r_s, \hat{t} t_s) + C_B^m(\hat{\xi} \xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}} r_s, \hat{t} t_s) \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

whereby the fact that the scaling factors are assumed to be constant was utilized. In the next step, the Eq. (4.12) is divided by the prefactor of the transient term.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial \hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t})}{\partial \hat{t}} + \frac{t_s}{r_s} \nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{r}}} \cdot \left(\mathbf{v}_{\mathbf{r}}(\hat{\xi}\xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}}r_s, \hat{t}t_s) \hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) \right) + \frac{t_s}{\xi_s} \frac{\partial}{\partial \hat{\xi}} \left(v_{\xi}(\hat{\xi}\xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}}r_s, \hat{t}t_s) \hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) \right) \\ &= \frac{t_s}{\xi_s^3} \frac{\hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t})}{V(\hat{\xi})} \frac{1}{\rho_d} \frac{dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} - \hat{B}_D^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) + \hat{B}_B^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) - \hat{C}_D^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) + \hat{C}_B^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

In which are

$$\hat{B}_D^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) = t_s b(\hat{\xi}\xi_s) \hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) \quad (4.14)$$

$$\hat{B}_B^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) = \xi_s t_s \rho_d(\hat{\xi}\xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}}r_s, \hat{t}t_s) V(\hat{\xi}) \int_{\hat{\xi}}^{\hat{\xi}_{\max}} \nu P(\hat{\xi}\xi_s, \hat{\zeta}\xi_s) b(\hat{\zeta}\xi_s) \frac{\hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\zeta}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t})}{\rho_d(\hat{\zeta}\xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}}r_s, \hat{t}t_s) V(\hat{\zeta})} d\hat{\zeta} \quad (4.15)$$

$$\hat{C}_D^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) = \frac{f_{d,s}^m t_s}{\xi_s^2} \hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) \int_{\hat{\xi}_{\min}}^{(\hat{\xi}_{\max} - \hat{\xi})^{1/3}} c(\hat{\xi}\xi_s, \hat{\zeta}\xi_s) \frac{\hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\zeta}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t})}{\rho_d(\hat{\zeta}\xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}}r_s, \hat{t}t_s) V(\hat{\zeta})} d\hat{\zeta} \quad (4.16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{C}_B^m(\hat{\xi}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t}) &= \frac{f_{d,s}^m t_s \xi_s^2 \rho_d(\hat{\xi}\xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}}r_s, \hat{t}t_s) V(\hat{\xi})}{\xi_s^2} \\ & \int_{\hat{\xi}_{\min}}^{(\hat{\xi}^3 - \hat{\xi}_{\min}^3)^{1/3}} \frac{c([\hat{\xi}^3 - \hat{\zeta}^3]^{1/3} \xi_s, \hat{\zeta}\xi_s) \frac{\hat{f}_d^m(\hat{\zeta}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t})}{\rho_d(\hat{\xi}\xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}}r_s, \hat{t}t_s) V(\hat{\zeta})}}{(\hat{\xi}^3 - \hat{\zeta}^3)^{2/3}} \\ & \frac{\hat{f}_d^m([\hat{\xi}^3 - \hat{\zeta}^3]^{1/3}, \hat{\mathbf{r}}, \hat{t})}{\rho_d([\hat{\xi}^3 - \hat{\zeta}^3]^{1/3} \xi_s, \hat{\mathbf{r}}r_s, \hat{t}t_s) V([\hat{\xi}^3 - \hat{\zeta}^3]^{1/3})} d\hat{\zeta} \end{aligned} \quad (4.17)$$

In a final step, the scaling factors are chosen. The following scaling factors are only suggestions and are generally case specific.

$$f_{d,s}^m = m_0 / \xi_{\max} \quad (4.18)$$

$$t_s = \tau \quad (4.19)$$

$$\mathbf{r}_s = (x_{\max}, y_{\max}, z_{\max})^T \quad (4.20)$$

$$\xi_s = \xi_{\max} \quad (4.21)$$

$$\zeta_s = \xi_{\max} \quad (4.22)$$

Here m_0 is initial mass of all particles in the modeled system per unit volume, τ the mean residence time of the particles in the modeled system. When extending this procedure to a number-based PBE, the prefactors remain consistent with mass-based PBEs for all terms except coalescence. The prefactor for the coalescence term in the number-based form becomes $f_{d,s}^n t_s \xi_s$. Note that the consecutive equations e.g. $\rho_d, b(\hat{\xi}\xi_s)$ are calculated with dimensional quantities and have a dimension themselves. The consecutive equations can also be nondimensionalized, although the prefactors must then be included in to the consecutive equation and any dimensional prefactors that occur in the consecutive equations must also be scaled.

From preliminary studies we were able to observe that the nondimensionalization reduces the computing time but hardly affects the accuracy. However, the challenge associated with the denominator in the coalescence birth term persists partially, prompting consideration of alternative strategies, including additional operations on nondimensionalized coordinates, such as applying

the natural logarithm. Alternatively, the PBE could be derived directly with dimensionless inner coordinates. This derivation requires careful reformulation of breakage and coalescence integrals from the general form (cf. Jakobsen [13]) and precise transformation of the corresponding kernels. Exploration of these approaches is pending and will be a focus of future investigations.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

In this study, the number-based PBE was derived on the basis of a generalized multidimensional transport equation stemming from continuum mechanics and then transformed into a mass-based PBE. This transformation revealed an additional term in the mass-based formulation, signifying the system's mass increase due to external mass transfer. We extensively discussed the origin and distinctions between this approach and the direct derivation of the mass-based PBE from the generalized transport equation. Our exploration demonstrated that growth rates in the property space are either mass or number conserving, depending on the derivation origin, a characteristic retained post-transformation, introducing an extra term in the PBE.

Based on a general growth velocity for particle lengths, we attribute the distinct conservation properties to mass transfer. The derivation of the number-based PBE is grounded in number-conserving mass transfer, leading to an increase in mass upon transformation into a mass-based PBE.

Furthermore, using our continuum mechanics approach, we derived the same PBE that includes the additional mass transfer term, consistent with the derivation by Vik *et al.* [10] from a kinetic gas theory approach.

Additionally, we addressed the numerical challenges arising from the denominator in the coalescence term after transformation, proposing nondimensionalization as a potential solution. Although this method partially resolved numerical issues, a notable enhancement in computational speed was observed.

In conclusion, this work significantly contributes to advancing the understanding of mass-based PBE modeling, unraveling intricacies in conservation properties and offering insights into addressing numerical challenges associated with certain terms.

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Nomenclature

Latin Letters

$B_B^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$	Number-based breakage birth term; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	$\text{m}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$
$B_D^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$	Number-based breakage death term; ; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	$\text{m}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$
$b(\xi)$	Breakage frequency	s^{-1}
c	c -coordinate of the property space	
\mathcal{C}	Phase space	
\mathbf{c}	Property space with internal coordinates $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots)^T$	
$C_B^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$	Number-based coalescence birth term; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	$\text{m}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$
$C_D^n(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$	Number-based coalescence death term; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	$\text{m}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$
$c(\xi, \zeta)$	Coalescence frequency	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
$f_d^n(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t)$	Number-based density function; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	
\mathbf{J}	Non-convective diffusive fluxes in phase space	
$m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$	Mass of one particle with size ξ	kg
m_0	Initial mass all particles in the system per unit volume	kg m^{-3}
N	Number of dimensions	-
\mathbf{n}_c	Local outer normal vector of $\delta\Omega_{\mathcal{C}}$	
$P(\xi, \zeta)$	Daughter size distribution function	m^{-1}
\mathbf{r}	Physical space with external coordinates $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)^T$; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	m
t	Time dimension; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	s
\mathbf{v}_r	Velocity in physical space	m s^{-1}
\mathbf{v}_c	Velocity in property space	
$V_d(\xi)$	Volume of the particle with size ξ	m^3
$v_\xi(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$	Velocity in particle size property space, growth rate; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	m s^{-1}
x	x -coordinate of the physical space	m
y	y -coordinate of the physical space	m
z	z -coordinate of the physical space	m

Greek Letters

$\delta\Omega_C$	Boundary of the phase space manifold; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	
ζ	Integration variable resp. the mother particle; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	m
ν	Average number of daughter particle after breakage	-
ξ	Particle size resp. daughter size; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	m
ρ_d	Mass density of the dispersed phase	kg m^{-3}
τ	Mean residence time of the particles in the system	s
Φ	Source or sink within the phase space	
ϕ	Arbitrary function	
$\dot{\psi}_0$	Nucleation rate in the property space	
Ψ	Conserved quantity	
ψ	Conserved density function	
Ω_C	Phase space manifold; see subscripts and superscripts for further variants	

Subscripts

B	Birth/ source term
<i>c</i>	Property space related quantity
<i>C</i>	Phase phase related quantity
d	Dispersed gas phase
D	Death/ sink term
<i>i</i>	Dimension index
ini	Initial quantity
max	Upper bound
min	Lower bound
part	Part of a surface
<i>r</i>	Physical space related quantity
ξ	Particle size related quantity
s	Scaling quantity

Superscripts

$\hat{}$	Dimensionless quantity
*	Incompletely transformed quantity
inlet	Quantity at the inlet
m	Mass-based quantity
n	Number-based quantity
outlet	Quantity at the outlet

continued . . .

... continued

T Transposed quantity

Abbreviations

KGT	Kinetic gas theory
KTAWSR	Kinetic theory approach with size resolution
mPBE	mass-based PBE
nPBE	number-based PBE
n2mPBE	mass-based PBE resulting of a transformation of a number-based PBE
PBE	Population balance equation

S. Supplementary Information

S.1. Derivation of a Generalized Transport Equation in \mathbb{R}^N

S.1.1. Mathematical Preamble

Gauss's Theorem

The Gauss's theorem can be generalized as follows:

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla \cdot \psi \, d^N \mathbf{C} = \oint_{\delta\Omega} \psi \cdot d^{N-1} \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{S.1})$$

where Ω is a bounded manifold in \mathbb{R}^N with N as the number of independent dimensions, ψ is a conserved density function and can be scalar or tensorial, \mathbf{C} is the phase space and $\delta\Omega$ is the boundary of the manifold Ω .

Total Time Derivative

The total (time) derivative is defined as follows:

$$\frac{d\phi(t, x_1(t), \dots, x_N(t))}{dt} = \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial t} + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{dx_i}{dt} \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x_i} \quad (\text{S.2})$$

where ϕ is a differential function, N is the number of dimensions and x_i a coordinate.

Generalized Leibniz's Rule

The Leibniz's rule can be generalized as follows:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega(t)} \psi \, d^N \mathbf{C} = \int_{\Omega(t)} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} d^N \mathbf{C} + \oint_{\delta\Omega(t)} \psi \, \mathbf{v} \cdot d^{N-1} \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{S.3})$$

$$= \int_{\Omega(t)} \left[\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\psi \, \mathbf{v}) \right] d^N \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{S.4})$$

where Eq. (S.1) was used.

S.1.2. Model Development

Fig. S.1 shows a finite control volume in the Lagrangian frame of reference for single phase flow.

Figure S.1.: Finite control volume in the Lagrangian frame of reference.

Form the balance of the conserved quantity, Ψ the Eq. (S.5) can be formulated. The conserved quantity Ψ can change in time by sources inside Φ or by non-convective fluxes \mathbf{J} across the interface of Ω .

$$\frac{d\Psi}{dt} = \int_{\Omega(t)} \Phi d^N \mathbf{C} - \oint_{\delta\Omega(t)} \mathbf{J} \cdot d^{N-1} \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{S.5})$$

Note that the axiom of continuum mechanics applies here, which states that quantities like Φ is continuous in the control volume, so that the integral can be formulated and applied without jumps. The conserved quantity Ψ is determined from the conserved density function ψ :

$$\Psi = \int_{\Omega(t)} \psi d^N \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{S.6})$$

If Eq. (S.6) is substituted into Eq. (S.5), it follows:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega(t)} \psi d^N \mathbf{C} = \int_{\Omega(t)} \Phi d^N \mathbf{C} - \oint_{\delta\Omega(t)} \mathbf{J} \cdot d^{N-1} \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{S.7})$$

Apply the Gauss's theorem Eq. (S.1) to the non-convective flux term:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega(t)} \psi d^N \mathbf{C} = \int_{\Omega(t)} \Phi d^N \mathbf{C} - \int_{\Omega(t)} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} d^N \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{S.8})$$

Apply the generalized Leibniz's rule Eq. (S.4) on the left hand side of Eq. (S.8) results:

$$\int_{\Omega(t)} \left[\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\psi \mathbf{v}) \right] d^N \mathbf{C} = \int_{\Omega(t)} \Phi d^N \mathbf{C} - \int_{\Omega(t)} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} d^N \mathbf{C} \quad (\text{S.9})$$

The volume integral must be fulfilled for every manifold Ω so that the following applies:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\psi \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = \Phi \quad (\text{S.10})$$

The Eq. (S.10) is a local instantaneous transport equation of the conserved density function ψ in multi-dimensional phase space in single phase flow.

For a practical application, the phase space \mathbf{C} is conventionally partitioned into physical space, characterized by external coordinates $\mathbf{r} = (x, y, z)^T$, and property space, defined by internal coordinates $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, c_2, c_3, \dots)^T$. Since the individual dimensions of the phase space are in-dependent to each other, it can be separated as follows:

$$\mathbf{C} = \{\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{c}\} \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^3 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^{N-3} \quad (\text{S.11})$$

$$\mathbf{v} = \{\mathbf{v}_r, \mathbf{v}_c\} \quad (\text{S.12})$$

$$\nabla = \{\nabla_r, \nabla_c\} \quad (\text{S.13})$$

So that we get the generalized transport equation:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \nabla_r \cdot (\psi \mathbf{v}_r) + \nabla_c \cdot (\psi \mathbf{v}_c) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = \Phi \quad (\text{S.14})$$

With respect to population balance modeling, usually no diffusion is considered. If the influence of turbulence or dispersion is to be incorporated in the PBE, a diffusion term occurs. However, in general $\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{0}$ is set so that the generalized PBE appears:

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \nabla_r \cdot (\psi \mathbf{v}_r) + \nabla_c \cdot (\psi \mathbf{v}_c) = \Phi \quad (\text{S.15})$$

It should be noted that the conclusions drawn in this document remain valid even without taking diffusion into account.

S.1.3. Initial and Boundary Conditions

For the time $t = t_{\min}$, the conserved density function must be specified for the entire phase space

$$\psi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) = \psi_{\text{ini}}(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}) \quad t \in t_{\min} \quad (\text{S.16})$$

where t_{\min} is the lower boundary of the time domain.

Since Eq. (2.1) contains two first-order partial differential operators, boundary conditions must be set for each dimension of the physical and property space. For a better discussion of the boundary conditions, Eq. (2.1) is integrated over the entire phase space and Gauss's theorem Eq. (S.1) is applied.

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = \int_{\Omega(t)} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} d\mathbf{C} = \int_{\Omega(t)} \Phi d\mathbf{C} - \oint_{\delta\Omega_r(t)} \psi \mathbf{v}_r \cdot d\mathbf{r} - \oint_{\delta\Omega_c(t)} \psi \mathbf{v}_c \cdot d\mathbf{c} \quad (\text{S.17})$$

For the physical space, if we have an open domain, parts of the boundary surface is usually defined as inflow $\psi \mathbf{v}_r$ at $\delta\Omega_{r,\text{part}}^{\text{inlet}}$ and others as outflow $\psi \mathbf{v}_r$ at $\delta\Omega_{r,\text{part}}^{\text{outlet}}$. Only one of these two flows is set by the boundary condition usually the inflow the other the outflow is calculated by the differential equation. However, if we have a closed domain, the fluxes must be zero everywhere at the boundaries $\delta\Omega_r$. But since only one can be set to zero by the boundary condition, the other must become zero by the model formulation, e.g. by a suitable choice of model parameters and the constitutive equations. If these are not chosen correctly and there is a flux greater than zero at this boundary, the conservation quantity Ψ is lost, which contradicts the assumption of a closed domain. This applies in particular to the property space, because this is usually regarded as closed or partially closed or open. Partially closed or open means that one of the boundaries is open and the other is closed. A common case is nucleation of particles at the

lower boundary. Then we apply:

$$\dot{\psi}_0 = -(\mathbf{v}_c(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \mathbf{n}_c)\psi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) \quad \mathbf{c} \in \delta\Omega_{c,\min} \quad (\text{S.18})$$

$$0 = (\mathbf{v}_c(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \mathbf{n}_c)\psi(\mathbf{c}, \mathbf{r}, t) \quad \mathbf{c} \in \delta\Omega_{c,\max} \quad (\text{S.19})$$

where $\dot{\psi}_0$ is the nucleation rate and \mathbf{n}_c is the local outer normal vector of $\partial\Omega_c$. Eq. (S.18) then acts as the boundary condition and Eq. (S.19) must be fulfilled by the model formulation and is called regularity condition [14].

S.2. Derivation of Growth Velocity

The growth velocity is defined as the total (time) derivative of the inner coordinate. For the one-dimensional case of the particle length it applies:

$$v_\xi = \frac{d\xi}{dt} \quad (\text{S.20})$$

The change in particle length over time can also be calculated by the change in its volume using the total time derivative (cf. Eq. (S.2)):

$$v_\xi = \frac{\partial V_d(\xi)}{\partial \xi}^{-1} \frac{dV_d(\xi)}{dt} \quad (\text{S.21})$$

If the definition of mass density $\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$ is used, the change in particle volume over time can be related to a change in density and particle mass $m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)$ over time.

$$\frac{dV_d(\xi)}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \right) \quad (\text{S.22})$$

$$= \rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)^{-1} \frac{dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} - \rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)^{-2} m_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \frac{d\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} \quad (\text{S.23})$$

$$= \rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)^{-1} \frac{dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} - \rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)^{-1} V_d(\xi) \frac{d\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} \quad (\text{S.24})$$

If Eq. (S.24) is inserted into Eq. (S.21), the final equation for the growth rate for the one-dimensional length property case follows.

$$v_\xi = \left(\frac{dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} - V_d(\xi) \frac{d\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} \right) \left(\frac{\partial V_d(\xi)}{\partial \xi} \rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) \right)^{-1} \quad (\text{S.25})$$

This implies that growth can be attributed to changes in mass over time, resulting from mass transfer, or to changes in density over time, resulting from changes in temperature, pressure, or composition.

It is important to note that no additional assumptions were made during the derivation process. The resulting Eq. (S.25) is generally applicable to a one-dimensional length property that is affiliated with the particle's volume.

For spherical particles with $V_d(\xi) = \frac{\pi}{6} \xi^3$ it results:

$$v_\xi(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t) = -\frac{\xi}{3\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{d\rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} + \frac{1}{\frac{\pi}{2} \xi^2 \rho_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)} \frac{dm_d(\xi, \mathbf{r}, t)}{dt} \quad (\text{S.26})$$